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Adaptive Computational Framework to Infer Flaring Source Conditions from Remotely-Sensed Measurements of Methane Emissions

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ABSTRACT

Methane released through gas flaring slip accounts for a significant amount of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. While bottom-up (BU) remote sensing measurements of flaring systems can provide detailed data to inform emissions inventories, their accuracy and interpretation can be enhanced through the integration of high-fidelity computational models. In this study, we develop a high-fidelity computational framework that uses large eddy simulations with adaptive chemistry and adaptive meshing to numerically examine a laboratory-scale burner designed as a proof-of-concept measurement system to monitor methane emissions from natural gas flaring systems at field-scale. The framework is intended to be used as an accurate and computationally efficient companion to field-deployable measurement diagnostics to provide cross-validation of important BU methane emissions data, by supplying 3D flow, thermodynamic, and chemical information to complement 1D measurements and forming the basis for data assimilation and source condition inference. This integrated approach enhances the reliability and interpretability of observational data. We validated the computational framework using line-of-sight dual-comb laser spectroscopy measurements of temperature, water, methane mole fraction, and methane destruction removal efficiency above a fuel-rich, partially pre-

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mixed methane-air flame created by an industrial ribbon burner. We obtain good agreement between the experimental data and three-dimensional simulations for all four quantities. We also show that the present configuration can be accurately approximated using two-dimensional simulations and examine the effects of perturbing the inflow velocity and the equivalence ratio on flow, chemical, and thermodynamic properties. Using proper orthogonal decomposition, we find that the flow above the burner oscillates with a coherent global frequency of 8.14 Hz, and we show that oscillations in chemical quantities such as the methane reaction rate occur at a similar frequency. Finally, we extract the methane mass flux at various vertical locations above the burner and show non-monotonic behavior in this quantity resulting from unreacted methane above the flame and from flow acceleration accompanied by a change in momentum- to buoyancy-driven flow regimes. This result provides insights into how field measurements of methane mass flux may depend on the distance from the source and can inform the location and interpretation of source measurements.

KEYWORDS

Methane emissions; Adaptive mesh refinement; Tabulated adaptive chemistry; Differential diffusion; Proper orthogonal decomposition

1. Introduction

The increase in global average temperatures [1] has had detrimental effects on human health [2, 3], agricultural systems [4], natural ecosystems [5, 6], biodiversity [7], and economic outcomes [8]. This increase has been driven primarily by the increase in anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [9] and their added radiative forcing effects. Although methane (CH_4) emissions are only 2.5% of total carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions, measured in units of carbon mass flux, they represent approximately 31% of all anthropogenic radiative forcing through 2019 [10], given the 84-fold global warming potential (GWP) of CH_4 compared to CO_2 over a 20-year period [11]. Understanding, monitoring, and ultimately eliminating CH_4 emissions is therefore of crucial importance in limiting the global temperature rise to only 1.5°C, as targeted in the Paris Climate Agreement. Due to its relatively short atmospheric lifespan [10] and known sources, CH_4 emission control is a particularly attractive measure to achieve rapid progress towards the goals in the Paris Agreement.

Anthropogenic CH_4 emissions are, in part, driven by the production and use of

fossil fuels, which comprise approximately 34% of total global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions [10, 12]. Within the fossil fuel sector, CH₄ can be emitted by venting, in which unburned gas is released directly into the atmosphere, or by flaring, in which inefficient and incomplete combustion of fuels results in unreacted CH₄ escaping into the atmosphere (i.e., methane slip). Each of these practices is used during natural gas production to process excess gas that cannot be stored, is not needed due to intermittent demand, or is contaminated and cannot be used.

Flaring of gases, compared to venting, emits less CH₄ due to the consumption of the CH₄ as fuel. Government and industry studies have historically used the methane destruction removal efficiency (DRE), a measure of the amount of CH₄ downstream of the flare as a percentage of the source CH₄ concentration, as a metric to estimate total global CH₄ emissions originating from flaring, and have assumed a DRE of 98% based on idealized process conditions. However, several studies have found that this value is likely an underestimate. Plant et al. [13] used direct airborne sampling of CH₄ from flares in three different basins, including the effects of unlit flares or flares that blew out, and reported an approximately 91% total CH₄ DRE, a value that, if representative of DRE in gas flaring more broadly, would increase the estimate of total methane emissions by a factor of five. Innocenti et al. [14] used differential absorption lidar to measure DRE in flares at liquefied natural gas facilities and showed a wide range of values (83% to 99%) depending on flow conditions. Caulton et al. [15] used *in situ* airborne measurements and recovered a higher DRE of 99.8%, but only sampled continuously burning, non-sputtering flares, which are likely not representative of overall operating conditions. The International Energy Agency, in its 2024 global report on methane tracking, estimated a 92% DRE from gas flaring, resulting in 500 Mt of CO₂ equivalent annual GHG emissions [16].

Accurate inventories and estimates of CH₄ emissions and DRE are required for independent agencies to evaluate progress toward the near- and long-term goals established in global climate agreements, and to ultimately drive toward lower emissions in real world conditions. At the highest level, CH₄ emissions are inventoried using a top-down (TD) or bottom-up (BU) approach [17]. The TD approach aims to quantify CH₄ emissions by measuring concentrations and dispersion on regional scales and using model

inversion to translate observations into source-term estimates. To date, TD approaches with varying model fidelity have been used to describe methane emissions and emissions trajectories from point sources and to estimate, through inversion, a total source flux of CH_4 . The Gaussian plume model tracks the dispersion of methane using a highly simplified advection diffusion equation. The model is based on an analytical solution of the governing equations by assuming a point, steady-state emission source, constant and orthogonal wind velocity, and equal diffusion coefficients, and has been used in a number of studies on real emission events [18–20]. However, atmospheric conditions are rarely steady in reality, and plumes, even in the absence of cross-flow interaction, are known to exhibit periodic puffing behavior [21, 22]. Furthermore, inversion of the Gaussian plume model using high temporal resolution measurements would require long averaging windows [23]. The Gaussian plume model has thus been extended to the Gaussian puff model, which includes transient phenomena by relaxing steady-state assumptions and including periodic source and wind conditions [24, 25].

In contrast, the BU approach probes individual emitters at the source scale and extrapolates these data to sector-based emissions factors. If BU studies are performed on a statistically representative sample of a given sector activity, total sector emissions estimates can be computed by multiplying the sector-based emissions by an activity factor. This is advantageous compared to the TD approach because individual sector emissions can be isolated and industry-specific actions can be recommended. However, this approach requires data sets obtained from emitting sources operating at a wide (and ideally normally distributed) range of process and atmospheric conditions. Spurious, extreme, and highly temporally variable events skew these estimates. Ideally, BU results can be aggregated and compared with TD results. However, several comparisons between the two methods have shown significant disagreement in the total CH_4 emissions estimates [26–28].

The accuracy of BU-derived inventories largely depends on the quality of field measurements and the reliability of computational and analytical models in representing real processes and their emissions. Furthermore, based on the wide range of DRE assessments of gas flaring activity, additional work is needed to reach a more quantitative understanding of the physical mechanisms of DRE, including how DRE is affected

by process and environmental conditions and what emissions characteristics result from a representative distribution of process parameters. Finally, any model-based methods used to create local, sector-specific emissions estimates should ideally be coupled with field-deployable measurement diagnostics and cross-validated against the resulting data.

Numerous previous computational studies of individual flaring systems have been performed in an effort to more accurately inform BU estimates of CH_4 emissions. Similar to the present study, Stolzman et al. [29] used an OpenFOAM-based numerical framework to model a laboratory-scale proxy for a field-scale flaring system. The authors used large eddy simulations (LES) combined with a flamelet progress variable approach to model chemistry and demonstrated good agreement with extractive measurements of CO_2 . Mohit et al. [30] used a similar numerical framework to investigate the effects of crossflow turbulence intensity and nozzle geometry on flame combustion efficiency. Singh et al. [31] used ANSYS Fluent to study combustion efficiencies and species distributions in three different configurations using three different fuels. They obtained reasonable agreement with experimental measurements from Allen and Torres [32] for several species and temperature profiles above the burners, and also demonstrated the ability to model combustion efficiency in these cases. The experimental data from Allen and Torres [32], which includes both invasive and remote sensing diagnostics, was used again in a study by Damodara et al. [33], who developed a reduced chemical mechanism to study C_4 hydrocarbons and soot precursor distributions. Castineira and Edgar [34] used post-combustion gas sampling measurements from Kostiuk and Thomas [35] as validation data for Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes simulations of three-dimensional (3D) jet diffusion flames in cross-flow, representative of flaring configurations. This work showed good agreement between the simulation results and the experimental measurements of combustion efficiency for various cross-flow speeds, despite using a laminar flamelet combustion model and neglecting the effects of radiative heat transfer.

In the present study, we develop and validate an adaptive computational framework for the study of flaring source conditions by modeling a laboratory scale CH_4 /air ribbon burner operating under highly non-ideal, partially premixed combustion conditions [36]. The computational results are compared with measurements of in-flame chemical species mole fractions and temperatures from dual-comb spectroscopy (DCS) [36], which has

previously been shown to be an effective field diagnostic in remote and local sensing of CH_4 [37]. We examine the correspondence between 3D and two-dimensional (2D) simulations and then use the latter to study different inflow velocities and equivalence ratios. We quantify the dynamics of the burner using proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), and identify significant changes in the flow and chemistry as a function of time.

Ultimately, this is the first computational study to use DCS measurements for DRE validation, and the resulting computational framework can be used to explore the effects of changing process, geometry, and atmospheric conditions, as well as provide a baseline for experimental data assimilation. Furthermore, the present framework has been developed as a spatially and chemically adaptive tool to alleviate the computational burden of spanning the wide range of physical scales present in real-world systems, and can be used in the future to develop reduced-order models to extend usage to field-scale studies and parameterizations.

2. Numerical Models and Methods

2.1. Simulation Geometry and Physical Configuration

The present study models a laboratory-scale ribbon burner that has been extensively characterized by Alexander et al. [38] and Stroud et al. [39]. These authors noted that the nearly porous geometry of the burner inlet has advantageous effects for flame laminarization and attachment characteristics. The flame is created by feeding the burner with separate lines of methane and air, which are then mixed in a chamber of beads upstream from the burner surface to supply a homogeneous mixture.

We based our simulation geometry on ribbon burner experiments carried out by Coburn et al. [36], who used DCS to measure vertical profiles of temperature, water vapor (H_2O) mole fraction, and CH_4 mole fraction above the burner surface, as well as CH_4 DRE. These measurements were taken along the laser line of sight and integrated over the laser path. The semi-infinite geometry of the configuration is such that a 2D plane normal to the lines of sight accurately describes the mean flame structure. This correspondence will be shown in Section 3, where we compare the results of the 2D and 3D simulations.

Figure 1. Schematic of full 3D computational domain including the solid steel ribbon burner. The red dashed line indicates a representative path along which data was measured with DCS and analyzed in the present study. The computational mesh in the figure shows the plane along which 2D simulations were performed, in addition to the mesh in the 3D adaptive mesh simulations.

A schematic of the computational domain, including the 2D burner plane and laser line of sight, is shown in Fig. 1. The domain was divided into solid (i.e., burner) and fluid (i.e., gas) regions, the solutions of which were coupled via a conjugate heat transfer (CHT) boundary condition discussed in Section 2.2. The experiments carried out by Coburn et al. [36] prescribed a partially premixed fuel-rich inflow with a fuel equivalence ratio of 2.4. From measurements just above the burner surface, a CH_4 mole fraction of 0.212 was used to set the burner inflow equivalence ratio in the baseline simulations. In addition, we included a 0.1 m/s coflow of air on either side of the burner to aid in flame stabilization and mimic ambient entrainment in laboratory experiments.

The 3D simulations used a solid burner geometry that approximates the ribbon structure with equally spaced $1.25 \text{ mm} \times 1.25 \text{ mm}$ square ports. The premixed gas inflow velocity was then set by dividing the volumetric flow rate used in the experiment by the total open port area. This resulted in an inflow velocity of 1.05 m/s. The inflow velocity for the 2D simulations was prescribed by matching the total volumetric flow rate that would be recovered if the 2D geometry were projected to the correct 3D length and dividing the experimental flow rate by this projected surface area. This leads to

a nominal burner velocity of 0.55 m/s for the 2D case. The inflow temperature of the premixed gases was set at 400 K to recover the lowest experimental temperature data point, and the coflow temperature was set at 300 K to replicate the ambient laboratory conditions. An ambient pressure of 82 kPa was used to match the atmospheric pressure at which the experiments were carried out in Boulder, CO.

The computational domain for the 3D cases was $1\text{ m} \times 1.02\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m}$ in the x , y , and z directions, respectively. The base 3D mesh used a 0.02 m resolution with the mesh adaptively refined to 1.25 mm using the top 99% of hydroxide (OH) mole fraction and mixture fraction (Z) greater than 0.02. The domain for the 2D cases was $1\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m}$ in the x and y directions, as shown in Fig. 1. We discretized the 2D domain using a uniformly refined mesh with a static resolution of 0.625 mm. The simulations were initialized using a hydrostatic pressure field under quiescent conditions. Boundary conditions on the sides of the domain were outflows with a prescribed inflow concentration or zero gradient (in the case of velocity inflow and temperature). We used a zero-gradient boundary condition for the velocity at the top of the domain during outflow and a flux-based condition in the normal direction for inflow. The solid boundaries of the burner were initialized at 500 K with a no-penetration, no-slip velocity condition and a dynamic temperature condition using fluid-solid heat flux due to convection and radiation, as discussed in Section 2.2.

2.2. Numerical Methodology

The present simulations used the numerical framework `multiRegionFireDyMFoam` in `OpenFOAM` [40], which extends the finite-volume solver `fireFoam` to include functionality for adaptive mesh refinement and multi-region CHT. Conservation equations for mass, momentum, species, and enthalpy were solved using a second-order backward temporal discretization, second-order linear discretization schemes for all gradients, Laplacian, and flux schemes, and second-order linear upwind stabilized discretization for the divergence of velocity. The velocity and pressure solutions were coupled using the PIMPLE algorithm, which combines the SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations) and PISO (Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators) algorithms.

The conservation equations for mass and momentum are given by

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (2)$$

where the viscous stress tensor ($\boldsymbol{\tau}$) is

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \rho \nu [\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^\top] - \frac{2}{3} \rho \nu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \boldsymbol{\delta}. \quad (3)$$

In the above equations, ρ is the density, \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector, p is the thermodynamic pressure, \mathbf{g} is the gravity vector, and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

In this work, our objective was to accurately predict the distributions of chemical species in a low Reynolds number (Re), laminar, partially premixed flame. However, as several previous studies have shown [41–43], differential diffusion (i.e., the diffusion of multiple molecular species according to their individual and respective transport properties) can play an important and non-negligible role in determining species distributions, especially in laminar or transitional regions of mixed regime flames. We therefore solved governing equations for species and enthalpy that depart from the unity Lewis number (Le) assumption and compute mixture-averaged binary species diffusion coefficients D_k using the formulation by Sherwood and Reid [44] based on the Chapman-Enskog kinetic theory of gases. The mixture-averaged binary diffusion coefficients were computed as

$$D_k = \frac{1 - Y_k}{\sum_{j \neq k} X_j / D_{k,j}}, \quad (4)$$

where Y_k and X_j are the species mass and mole fractions, respectively, and the individual binary diffusion coefficients, $D_{k,j}$, of species k in species j were calculated using

$$D_{k,j} = \frac{0.0266 T^{3/2}}{p \sqrt{W_{k,j}} \sigma_{k,j}^2 \Omega_{k,j}}. \quad (5)$$

Here, T is the temperature, $W_{k,j}$ is a binary molecular weight between two species given by

$$W_{k,j} = \frac{2}{W_k^{-1} + W_j^{-1}}, \quad (6)$$

$\sigma_{k,j}$ is a binary molecular hard-sphere collision diameter given by

$$\sigma_{k,j} = \frac{\sigma_k + \sigma_j}{2}, \quad (7)$$

and $\Omega_{k,j}$ is a collision integral computed as

$$\Omega_{k,j} = \frac{A}{(T^*)^B} + \frac{C}{\exp(DT^*)} + \frac{E}{\exp(FT^*)} + \frac{G}{\exp(HT^*)}. \quad (8)$$

The dimensionless temperature T^* is given by $T^* = k_B T / \sqrt{\epsilon_k \epsilon_j}$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, ϵ_k and ϵ_j are the characteristic Lennard-Jones potentials, and the coefficients in Eq. (8) are [45] $A = 1.06036$, $B = 0.15610$, $C = 0.19300$, $D = 0.47635$, $E = 1.03587$, $F = 1.52996$, $G = 1.76474$, and $H = 3.89411$. Thermodynamic temperature and pressure were used for T and p , respectively, in Eq. (5), and W_i , ϵ_i , and σ_i for individual species are provided in the Appendix.

The resulting binary diffusion coefficients were used in the species transport and enthalpy equations given by

$$\frac{\partial(\rho Y_k)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho Y_k \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\rho D_k \nabla Y_k) + \omega_k, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial[\rho(h + K)]}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot [\rho(h + K) \mathbf{u}] = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \alpha \nabla h) - \sum_{k=1}^N \nabla [h_k (\rho D_k - \alpha)] \cdot \nabla Y_k + \dot{Q}_C + \dot{Q}_R, \quad (10)$$

where ω_k is the production rate of species k , h is the enthalpy, $K = (1/2) \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u}$ is the specific kinetic energy, α is the mixture-averaged thermal diffusivity computed thermodynamically using Sutherland and JANAF transport relationships, h_k is the contri-

bution of species k to the total specific enthalpy, and \dot{Q}_C is the heat release rate due to combustion (discussed in Section 2.3). The volumetric radiative power density, \dot{Q}_R , in Eq. (10) was calculated by assuming a non-absorbing optically thin gas and solving the radiative transfer equation using the finite-volume discrete ordinate model over a discrete number of solid elementary angles, Ω , as

$$\dot{Q}_R = \int_{4\pi} \frac{dI}{ds} d\Omega = \chi_r \dot{Q}_C, \quad (11)$$

where I is the radiative intensity, s is the path length along each ray, and χ_r is a global radiative fraction set at $\chi_r = 0.15$, a value supported by other methane flame studies [46–48] and by the present validation effort.

The fluid and solid region solutions were coupled using a mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary condition on the region interface temperature. This boundary condition equates the solid temperature (T_s) gradient with the fluid temperature (T_f) gradient on the surface using

$$\kappa_s \nabla T_s = -\kappa_f \nabla T_f - \dot{\mathbf{q}}_r, \quad (12)$$

where κ_s is the solid thermal conductivity, $\kappa_f = \mu C_{p,f}$ is the fluid thermal conductivity, μ is the dynamic viscosity, and $C_{p,f}$ is the specific heat capacity of the fluid. The radiative flux at the interface, $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_r$, is an output of the radiation model. The fluid-solid interface temperatures are assumed to be equal (i.e., $T_{f,\text{int}} = T_{s,\text{int}}$), allowing the above equation to be solved in terms of a single interface temperature. The enthalpy within the solid domain was calculated as

$$\rho_s \frac{\partial h_s}{\partial t} = \alpha_s \nabla^2 h_s, \quad (13)$$

where α_s is the thermal diffusivity of the solid phase calculated as $\alpha_s = \kappa_s / \rho_s C_{p,s}$ and ρ_s and $C_{p,s}$ are the density and specific heat capacity respectively in the solid.

2.3. Chemical Kinetic Model

In the present premixed flame simulations, fuel and oxidizer are initialized together in computational cells. This precludes the use of infinitely fast chemistry models, which drive mixtures to an immediate reaction based on highly simplified global chemical mechanisms. In contrast, the present simulations require the computation of finite rate chemical reaction coefficients, which are then used to solve a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) defining the time rate of change of individual species concentrations. For example, as described in Turns [45], for the reaction

where k_f and k_r are the forward and reverse reaction rate coefficients, respectively, we can calculate the concentration of A by integrating the following ODE in time

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -k_f[A][B] + k_r[C][D], \quad (14)$$

where $[\cdot]$ denotes a concentration. Each reaction in a chemical mechanism will be defined by its own forward and reverse reaction rate coefficients, which were computed in the present framework using a temperature-dependent Arrhenius equation given by

$$k_{i,j}(T) = A_{i,j} T^{b_{i,j}} \exp[-(E_A)_{i,j}/R_u T], \quad (15)$$

where $k_{i,j}$ is the coefficient for the i th reaction in either the forward ($j = f$) or reverse ($j = r$) direction, $A_{i,j}$ is a pre-exponential factor, $b_{i,j}$ is an exponential factor, $(E_A)_{i,j}$ is the activation energy required for a reaction to progress, and R_u is the universal gas constant. As more species and more reactions are added to a given mechanism, the number of ODEs will increase, and each ODE will contain more terms with associated reaction rate coefficients. Furthermore, larger mechanisms can contain species that react at drastically different rates, leading to a system of stiff ODEs [49]. This greatly reduces the computational efficiency of a simulation by requiring small chemical time steps and introducing potential numerical instability.

In this work, we used the Tabulated Dynamic Adaptive Chemistry (TDAC) method, which combines the In Situ Adaptive Tabulation (ISAT) method described by Pope [50] with the Dynamic Adaptive Chemistry (DAC) method from Liang et al. [51] to mitigate the numerical stiffness problem. This method has been used successfully within the OpenFOAM framework and has been shown to achieve substantial computational speedups compared to direct ODE integration methods [52–54]. The TDAC method works by initially solving the full set of ODEs via direct integration given a specific composition. The results are then stored and tabulated in a set of “leaves”. When the composition at a later time is within a defined ellipsoid of accuracy (EOA) – that is, close to previous compositions that produced previously tabulated results – the solution is retrieved from the tabulated leaves and reused. If the composition falls outside the EOA, new leaves must be added. Here, the composition and thermodynamic properties are fed to the DAC to compute a reduced mechanism to be solved, and the solutions are added to the table in the form of new leaves.

In the present study, we used the DRM19 mechanism [55] outlined in the Appendix, which consists of 21 total species and 84 reactions, combined with TDAC to solve for the reaction rates ω_k . These rates were then used to calculate \dot{Q}_C in Eq. (10) as

$$\dot{Q}_C = \sum_k^N -\omega_k h_{f,k}, \quad (16)$$

where $h_{f,k}$ is the enthalpy of formation for species k .

3. Results and Discussion

Coburn et al. [36] used near-infrared DCS to measure the temperature, H₂O mole fraction, CH₄ mole fraction, and CH₄ DRE at various heights above a ribbon burner. The measurements were taken by traversing a laser system across an array of heights and sending the laser light along the z direction, as shown in Fig. 1. Absorption signals were then post-processed for each data point by performing nonlinear fits using the HITEMP spectral database and obtaining path-integrated values for each quantity. Coburn et al. [36] noted a potential 4% error in fitting using the HITEMP database.

Figure 2. Simulated time-averaged ($\langle \cdot \rangle_t$) vertical profiles of temperature (a), H_2O mole fraction (b), and CH_4 mole fraction (c) above the ribbon burner compared with DCS measurements and their respective experimental uncertainties from [36]. In the 3D simulations, we additionally include path averaging ($\langle \cdot \rangle_{zt}$). Blue shading corresponds to the baseline 2D case and four additional 2D cases at the extents of the experimental uncertainty bounds: -10% burner inflow rate and $\pm 4\%$ CH_4 inflow mole fraction; and $+10\%$ burner inflow rate and $\pm 4\%$ CH_4 inflow mole fraction.

Although this has little effect on the locations closest to the burner for temperature and H_2O , due to their low values at these locations, significant differences in CH_4 are observed. In addition, Coburn et al. [36] noted uncertainty in the accuracy of the flow controller, since the lowest CH_4 measurement was higher than that of the controller, leading to a slightly higher equivalence ratio of 2.6.

In the simulations, we used the experimental uncertainties in both the flow rate and the equivalence ratio to inform bounds on computational boundary conditions for the burner velocity and burner CH_4 mass fraction, ultimately providing uncertainty bounds for the simulation results. Specifically, we performed one baseline 3D simulation using the experimentally measured values for temperature and CH_4 at a height of 1 mm above the burner. We then performed a series of five 2D simulations consisting of the baseline case, two cases with the inflow velocity perturbed by -10% and the CH_4 mole fraction by $\pm 4\%$, and two cases with the inflow velocity perturbed by $+10\%$ and the CH_4 mole fraction by $\pm 4\%$. The 2D simulations, which could be performed much more quickly than the 3D simulations, were used to provide uncertainty bounds on the simulation results.

3.1. Mean Flow Structure

Figure 2 shows that the results from the 3D simulation agree well with the time- and path-averaged vertical profiles of temperature (T) and CH_4 mole fraction (X_{CH_4}) from the experiments. This figure also shows that the 2D and 3D baseline results are nearly identical for all quantities. Although there are larger differences between the simulations and experiments for $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ in Fig. 2(b) further from the burner, the uncertainty limits from the 2D simulations fully encompass the experimental data for each quantity and all heights, except for the two uppermost experimental measurements of $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. We speculate on the reasons for these differences in Section 4.

As discussed in Section 1, gas flaring is performed primarily as a method to remove CH_4 through combustion, in exchange for the emission of less potent GHGs such as CO_2 . In part, the aim of the present study is to establish an accurate and reliable joint computational and experimental framework that can be used to assess the efficiency of CH_4 destruction in real-world systems. The most widely used metric for assessing this is DRE, which is defined as

$$\text{DRE} = 100\% \times \left(\frac{X_{\text{CH}_4,0} - X_{\text{CH}_4}}{X_{\text{CH}_4,0}} \right), \quad (17)$$

where $X_{\text{CH}_4,0}$ is the CH_4 mole fraction at the initial measurement location and X_{CH_4} is the mole fraction at each subsequent location. A DRE of 100% indicates that all CH_4 present at the source exists at that location, and a DRE of 0% indicates that there is no CH_4 present at that location. The comparison of experimental and simulation DRE in Fig. 3 shows that the numerical framework is able to accurately predict DRE for the present configuration. Furthermore, as will be shown in Section 3.4, this agreement allows us to use the 3D simulations to understand CH_4 emissions characteristics outside of these discrete measurement locations.

3.2. Temporal Dynamics

The flames in this study were observed to oscillate with a regular coherent puffing frequency. This phenomenon has been extensively studied in both reacting and non-

Figure 3. Methane destruction removal efficiency (DRE) from Eq. (17) for the experimental (crosses) and simulation (solid line and shading) data at various heights above the burner. Blue shading corresponds to the baseline 2D case and four additional 2D cases at the extents of the experimental uncertainty bounds: -10% burner inflow rate and $\pm 4\%$ CH_4 inflow mole fraction; and $+10\%$ burner inflow rate and $\pm 4\%$ CH_4 inflow mole fraction. The 2D cases are time-averaged (i.e., $\langle \text{DRE} \rangle_t$) and the 3D cases are time- and path-averaged (i.e., $\langle \text{DRE} \rangle_{zt}$)

reacting buoyant flows [21, 22, 56]. From the perspective of field sensing of real flaring systems, it could be useful to quantify this effect and to understand its degree of coupling with oscillatory behavior in chemical processes (e.g., DRE), especially because it is hard to directly study in real flaring systems. A robust method for tracking this behavior could support the development of computationally efficient and reduced-order models for field-scale applications. To this end, we begin by probing the mean subtracted vertical velocity, $u'_y = u_y - \langle u_y \rangle_t$, above the center of the burner for the baseline 3D case, where $\langle \cdot \rangle_t$ denotes a time average. Because the choice of probe vertical location is somewhat subjective, we include time series of u'_y taken at three different heights: 0.01 m, 0.02 m, and 0.03 m.

The results in Fig. 4(a) show that, for the three probe locations, a coherent oscillating u'_y signal is obtained with more pronounced amplitudes at higher vertical locations. In Fig. 4(b), a Fourier transform of the signals shows that each of the probe locations exhibits a dominant oscillatory frequency of 8.14 Hz. To disambiguate the thermodynamic and flow oscillations, we also extracted time series of the mean subtracted temperature,

Figure 4. Time series of the mean-subtracted vertical velocity (a) and temperature (c) probed at three different vertical locations, and power spectral densities of the vertical velocity (b) and temperature (d) signals taken from the 3D simulations.

$T' = T - \langle T \rangle_t$, at the same vertical locations. These signals, along with their power spectral densities (PSDs) obtained using Fast Fourier Transforms (FFTs), are shown in Figs. 4(c) and 4(d) respectively, where we observe the same 8.14 Hz dominant frequency as observed in the u'_y signals.

Although the results in Fig. 4 show that, for the present configuration, the extraction of a dominant coherent puffing frequency did not suffer from the choice of measurement probe location, this may not be the case for more complex 3D flows. Moreover, FFTs do not reveal the dominant spatial structures associated with the oscillations. To address these issues, we use POD to extract a probe location-independent and more global metric of puffing frequency. This and the closely related singular value decomposition (SVD) method have been used successfully in numerous studies to extract coherent structures in buoyant flows [57–59]. In the present study, we use the POD method of snapshots, originally developed by Sirovich [60], to decompose the temperature fields in the baseline 3D case.

The POD method decomposes the fluctuating component of a generic vector field $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ into a linear combination of spatial modes, ϕ_j , and temporal coefficients, a_j , as

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \langle \mathbf{q} \rangle_t(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_j a_j(t) \phi_j(\mathbf{x}), \quad (18)$$

by finding the optimal basis of vectors that best represents the input data through

Figure 5. Spatial modes ϕ_1 (a), ϕ_2 (b), and ϕ_3 (c) obtained by performing snapshot POD on fluctuating temperature fields.

solving the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{R}\Phi = \Lambda\Phi, \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{R} is a covariance matrix formed by taking the inner product $\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^T$, \mathbf{X} is the snapshot matrix, which is constructed with $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \langle \mathbf{q} \rangle_t(\mathbf{x})$ at each time, reshaped into column vectors, Φ is a matrix containing the eigenvectors (ϕ_j), and Λ is a diagonal matrix containing the eigenvalues (λ_j). In a more computationally efficient method for large snapshot matrices, we decompose \mathbf{X} directly through SVD using

$$\mathbf{X} = \Phi\Sigma\Psi^T, \quad (20)$$

where Ψ is a matrix containing the right singular vectors, and Σ is a diagonal matrix containing the singular values of \mathbf{X} , which are related to the eigenvalues by $\sigma_j^2 = \lambda_j$.

The first three spatial modes for the fluctuating temperature field are shown in Figs. 5(a-c). We note that due to the pairwise similarities of modes 1 and 2, 3 and 4, and 5 and 6, we denote modes 1, 3, and 5 as the first three modes. An oscillatory vertically propagating structure is clearly visible in modes 1 and 3 in Fig. 5, while mode

Figure 6. Temporal coefficients a_1 - a_3 corresponding to modes 1 (a), 2 (c), and 3 (e) with the respective power spectral densities of each signal (from POD on temperature fields).

2 is indicative of the shear layer structure at the outer edges of the flame.

As described in Eq. (18), POD also provides a set of singular right vectors a_j that describe the temporal dynamics of each ϕ_j . The first three a_j signals are shown in Fig. 6, along with each of their respective PSDs. It is notable that the first and most energetic mode, as shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b), oscillates at the same dominant frequency computed in Fig. 4.

The singular values and corresponding temporal and spatial modes are ordered in terms of the optimality with which they capture the decomposed field from a least squares perspective. As dictated by the decomposition in Eq. (18), we would need all modes to recover the full field variance. However, we can also reasonably represent the field variance with a reduced rank Φ . Individual singular values (σ_j) represent the contributions of each mode to the total variance. In Fig. 7, we compute a cumulative sum of σ_j^2 using $\sum_{j=1}^k \sigma_j^2 / \sum_{j=1}^N \sigma_j^2$ and observe that 80% of the variance is captured in the first five modes, indicating that the present flow has the potential to be accurately described using a reduced rank representation.

Figure 7. Cumulative sum of singular values computed using POD on the temperature field.

3.3. Chemical State Analysis

The preceding analysis examined the oscillatory behavior of the flame from a flow and thermodynamic perspective. We can further examine whether oscillatory behavior is also exhibited in the chemical dynamics and to what degree this behavior is coupled with the flow. To do this, we examine instantaneous fields of T , X_{CH_4} , and the log-modulus of the CH_4 reaction rate, denoted $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$, where $\mathcal{L}(x) = \text{sign}(x) \log_{10}[(1 + |x|)]$. This particular transformation is used to preserve magnitudes and zero values while distinguishing between positive and negative values across a wide range of magnitudes.

Figure 8 shows snapshots of T , X_{CH_4} , and $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$, at times approximately one-half of the period extracted in the previous analysis to observe similar oscillatory behavior in these fields. This corresponds to approximately 0.06 s between each snapshot. We first examine these fields along an x -normal plane and threshold $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ at values of X_{CH_4} greater than 10^{-6} . The first snapshot in Fig. 8(a), taken at 1.63 s, shows that a quasi-diffusion flame forms at the lower extents of the flame with a thin high-temperature reaction zone present below approximately 0.05 m. The nearly 400 K flame core then begins to increase in temperature and a more uniform high-temperature zone is formed above approximately 0.05 m. The contour of the stoichiometric mixture frac-

Figure 8. Instantaneous snapshots from the x -normal plane at times 1.63 s, 1.69 s, and 1.75 s (left to right) of temperature, CH_4 mole fraction, and log modulus of CH_4 reaction rate (top to bottom). The black dotted lines indicate the contours of Z_{st} (shown as white dotted lines in panels d-f).

tion (Z_{st}) closely follows the diffusion-like reaction zone in the lower part of the flame and begins to close in the spanwise direction at approximately 0.15 m.

For the snapshot at 1.63 s, Fig. 8(d) shows that the CH_4 mole fraction (X_{CH_4}) exhibits nearly uniform dissipation from the burner inlet to the top of the flame. However, in Fig. 8(g) we observe a much more non-uniform distribution in $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$, with large magnitude negative values within the reaction zone, indicating fast consumption and destruction of CH_4 , and near-zero values in the flame core until approximately 0.05 m. This zone of near-zero $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ appears to correlate well with the shape of large regions of X_{CH_4} . This, combined with the fact that a vertical gradient is observed in X_{CH_4} up to 0.05 m, where no vertical gradient in $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ is observed, is indicative of reactions occurring most vigorously on the outer spanwise extents of the flame where the equiva-

lence ratio is close to stoichiometric. Furthermore, in this snapshot, we observe a closing of the reaction zone in the form of a more negative $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ tip in the flame core at approximately 0.05 m, followed by a region from near-zero to slightly positive $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ from about 0.05 m to 0.1 m. This indicates a non-consumption zone of X_{CH_4} in the flame core where X_{CH_4} is produced at low rates.

In the next snapshot, at 1.69 s, Fig. 8(h) show that the region of low CH_4 consumption within the flame core appears to pinch off and propagate vertically. In particular, this pinched segment is outside the contour of Z_{st} , indicating a low probability of further consumption. Finally, at 1.75 s, the structures in all three fields in Figs. 8(c), 8(f), and 8(i) return to a state similar to that observed 0.12 s earlier at 1.63 s. This periodicity indicates that oscillations in chemical dynamics are highly correlated with flow oscillations.

We observe similar oscillatory behavior in snapshots of the same fields along the z -normal plane in Fig. 9. Here, the banded structure of $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ is even more apparent. That is, in the first and third snapshots in Figs. 9(g) and 9(i), we observe a diffusion flame structure until approximately 0.05 m, followed by a clear triangular region of low CH_4 consumption. This triangular zone is completely absent in the snapshot at 1.69 s. Additionally, in Figs. 9(d-f), we observe that a non-negligible amount of unburned CH_4 is advected laterally (i.e., in the x direction) outside of the Z_{st} contour, and then flows upward. Because DCS measurements examined lines of sight that did not encompass a path away from the burner, this excess CH_4 was not represented in Figs. 2 and 3. The implications of this are discussed later in this study.

There are various potential explanations for the slight and transient increase in X_{CH_4} within the flame core. Although global reactions for methanation (that is, production of CH_4) are not present in the DRM19 reaction mechanism, there are several reaction pathways that could lead to production. To begin to understand which of these pathways and which specific species are responsible for this phenomenon, we can examine the correlations between $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$ and the species mole fractions at the times shown in Figs. 8 and 9.

In Fig. 10(e), we observe a strong correlation between high OH concentrations and negative $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$, indicating that OH plays a role in the oxidation and destruction of

Figure 9. Instantaneous snapshots from the z -normal plane at times 1.63 s, 1.69 s, and 1.75 s (left to right) of temperature, CH_4 mole fraction, log modulus of CH_4 reaction rate (top to bottom). The black dotted lines indicate the contours of Z_{st} (shown as white dotted lines in panels d-f).

methane for a wide range of Z . In Fig. 10(c), we observe an inversely correlative trend, whereby lower values of O_2 correspond to more negative values of $\mathcal{L}(\omega_{\text{CH}_4})$, especially in the vicinity of Z_{st} , reflecting the consumption of CH_4 and O_2 within the flame. The temperature distribution in Fig. 10(f) shows that most regions of non-reacting CH_4 exist in regions of low temperature and away from Z_{st} . These trends shift in the 1.75 s snapshot of the same field distributions. Here, we observe correlations between high concentrations of H_2 (Fig. 11(a)) and CO (Fig. 11(d)) and zero to slightly positive CH_4 reaction rates. This same region is present in conjunction with high temperatures (Fig. 11(f)), a correlation that was also apparent in Figs. 8 and 9.

Figure 10. Instantaneous distributions of H_2 (a), CH_3 (b), O_2 (c), CO (d), and OH (e) mole fractions, and temperature (T) (f) as a function of mixture fraction (Z) at 1.69 s. The black dotted line indicates Z_{st} . Data points are colored by the log modulus of CH_4 reaction rate.

3.4. Methane Mass Flux

The present study aims to provide physical observations and relationships, supported by field-deployable measurement diagnostics, to better design BU measurement campaigns and models. While the quantities shown in Figs. 2 and 3 serve as valuable validation, they were only probed from within the flame. The ultimate CH_4 mass flux ($\mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4}$) over an entire 3D domain for a given set of process and atmospheric conditions is a key metric that can be used to inform CH_4 inventories and can disambiguate and enhance

Figure 11. Instantaneous distributions of H₂ (a), CH₃ (b), O₂ (c), CO (d), and OH (e) mole fractions, and temperature (T) (f) as a function of mixture fraction (Z) at 1.75 s. The black dotted line indicates Z_{st} . Data points are colored by the log modulus of CH₄ reaction rate.

spatially limited experimental measurement data. Accordingly, here we define a \mathcal{M}_{CH_4} that is computed in horizontal (i.e., y -normal) planes at 50 vertical locations across the full computational domain as

$$\mathcal{M}_{CH_4}(y) = \int_{x,z} \rho u_y Y_{CH_4} dA, \quad (21)$$

Figure 12. Time-averaged methane mass flux taken through y -normal planes within the domain (a), time- and planar-averaged methane mass fraction (b), and time- and planar-averaged vertical velocity with time- and planar-averaged Richardson number (c).

where Y_{CH_4} is the CH_4 mass fraction. We numerically calculate Eq. (21) over the full x - z horizontal plane at each vertical location (y) and then compute the time-averaged flux $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$. To understand the connection of variations in $\mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4}$ to flow or chemical phenomena, we further compute time-averaged profiles of Y_{CH_4} and u_y averaged over each horizontal plane, denoted $\langle Y_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_{xzt}$ and $\langle u_y \rangle_{xzt}$.

These results are shown in Fig. 12, where we observe non-monotonic behavior in $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$. Specifically, in Fig. 12(a), we observe an initially steep decrease in $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$ as much of the CH_4 quickly reacts and is removed, slowing the rate of $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$ due to lower concentrations of CH_4 . This trend continues until approximately 0.1 m, where we observe an increase in $\langle Y_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_{xzt}$ in Fig. 12(b), and a corresponding inflection in $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$ in Fig. 12(a). The increase in $\langle Y_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_{xzt}$ is supported by the observations made in Figs. 8, 9, 10, and 11 where unreacted CH_4 was present at this vertical location. We further note that the slightly positive values of ω_{CH_4} observed in Figs. 8, 9, 10, and 11 indicate that there are active reactions involved in producing small amounts of CH_4 in the presence of highly non-stoichiometric conditions. Figure 12(a) shows that $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4} \rangle_t$ continues to increase beyond 0.1 m, and this increase is further promoted by a flow acceleration in $\langle u_y \rangle_t$ at approximately 0.35 m, as shown in Fig. 12(c).

To further interrogate the origins of the flow acceleration, we plot the temporally- and spatially-averaged Richardson number, $\langle \text{Ri} \rangle_{xzt}$, in Fig. 12(c). We compute $\langle \text{Ri} \rangle_{xzt}$ at each y location using $\text{Ri} = (1 - \rho/\rho_\infty)gy/u_y^2$, where $\rho_\infty = 0.95 \text{ kg/m}^3$ to reflect ambient laboratory conditions, and observe a transition from a momentum-driven (i.e., $\langle \text{Ri} \rangle_{xzt} < 1$) to a buoyancy-driven (i.e., $\langle \text{Ri} \rangle_{xzt} > 1$) regime at approximately the same location where the flow begins to accelerate. The results in Fig. 12 demonstrate that estimates of either CH_4 concentrations or $\mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4}$ inferred from *in-situ* flame measurements can be complicated by chemical and flow phenomena that contribute to non-monotonic behavior in these quantities, especially in highly non-stoichiometric flames. The results further suggest that measurements should be taken at a wide range of heights and spanwise locations to most accurately estimate downstream $\mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4}$ from a given source.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed a computational framework that includes differential molecular diffusion, conjugate heat transfer, adaptive mesh refinement, and detailed adaptive tabulated chemistry to model a laminar, fuel-rich, partially premixed buoyant jet flame above an industrial ribbon burner. The study was motivated by the need for detailed models that can be validated against field-deployable measurement diagnostics to detect and measure CH_4 emissions from gas flaring. The adaptive functionality of the numerical framework enables field-scale studies to be performed at reasonable computational cost.

The present framework was first validated in 3D against DCS measurements of vertical profiles of temporally and path averaged T , $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, X_{CH_4} , and DRE above a laboratory-scale ribbon burner. Five additional 2D simulations were performed using boundary conditions of X_{CH_4} and u_y perturbed by $\pm 4\%$ and $\pm 10\%$, respectively, to estimate experimental uncertainty. We showed good agreement between simulation results and measurements of T , $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and X_{CH_4} , and near identical results between the 2D and 3D simulations. The experimental measurements were fully encompassed by the uncertainty bounds, except for the highest two measurements of the water mole fraction. Given the good agreement in temperature and methane mole fraction between

the simulations and experiments at these locations, it is likely that this difference is due to higher than expected ambient humidity, modeling inaccuracies in the mixing of combustion products with ambient air far from the burner, or additional uncertainty in the ribbon burner conditions (e.g., systematic lean of the flame due to room air currents), or some combination of these and other causes. Further investigation of the far field agreement between the simulations and experiments, including additional chemical species, is an important direction for future research that will require new DCS measurements and new simulations.

The results from the 3D simulations were analyzed to understand the relationships between flow and chemical oscillatory behavior and we found, using POD and an analysis of CH_4 reaction rate fields, that the two are strongly correlated. We first showed that the flames oscillated with a regular coherent frequency of 8.14 Hz as computed using both a local (probe-based) and global (POD) methodology. We then examined fields of ω_{CH_4} , X_{CH_4} , and T to show chemical state oscillations at roughly the same frequency. The chemical state was found to oscillate between largely CH_4 -destructive, and more non-reactive to slightly CH_4 -producing regimes. The more non-reactive regions of CH_4 were found to be correlated with increased concentrations of H_2 and CO .

Finally, we showed that the CH_4 mass flux $\mathcal{M}_{\text{CH}_4}$ within the domain had a non-monotonic behavior with an inflection point that correlated with the location of a change in flow regime from a momentum- to a buoyancy-driven flow, as defined by the local $\langle \text{Ri} \rangle_{xzt}$. Future work will focus on quantifying the frequency at which we observe oscillations in ω_{CH_4} for more complex flaring conditions, in addition to performing field-scale simulations in conjunction with further measurements.

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5. Appendix

Table 1. Transport coefficients for DRM19 [55].

Specie	W_i	ϵ_i	σ_i
H ₂	2.0160	38.0	2.92
H	1.0080	145.0	2.05
O	15.9990	80.0	2.75
O ₂	31.9980	107.4	3.46
OH	17.0070	80.0	2.75
H ₂ O	18.0150	572.4	2.6
HO ₂	33.0060	107.4	3.46
CH ₂	14.0270	144.0	3.8
CH ₂ (S)	14.0270	144.0	3.8
CH ₃	15.0350	144.0	3.8
CH ₄	16.0430	141.4	3.75
CO	28.0100	98.1	3.65
CO ₂	44.0090	244.0	3.76
HCO	29.0180	498.0	3.59
CH ₂ O	30.0260	498.0	3.59
CH ₃ O	31.0340	417.0	3.69
C ₂ H ₄	28.0540	280.8	3.97
C ₂ H ₅	29.0620	252.3	4.3
C ₂ H ₆	30.0700	252.3	4.3
N ₂	28.0140	97.53	3.62
AR	39.9500	136.5	3.33

DRM19 mechanism, which involves 19 species and 84 reactions [55].

